

Habitual Excellence: Navigating Global Challenges with Kurniawan Arif Maspul (Q&A Podcast Paper)

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Abstract

This podcast paper delves into the insightful conversation between host Muhammad Sidik and guest Kurniawan Arif Maspul, exploring the journey of cultivating excellent habits amidst diverse professional landscapes. Kurniawan shares his multifaceted career trajectory, spanning education, entrepreneurship in the coffee industry, and academic pursuits as an Indonesian diaspora. Throughout the discussion, Kurniawan reflects on the pivotal role of discipline, prayers, and strategic thinking in facing global work challenges. He emphasizes the significance of mental well-being, dietary habits, and physical activity in fostering positive habits for personal and professional growth. The paper concludes with Kurniawan's inspiring message urging listeners to embrace creativity and aspire for greatness while staying grounded in faith.

Keywords: *Habitual excellence, Global challenges, Personal development, Professional growth, Discipline, Strategic thinking, Mental well-being, Physical activity, Problem-solving, Creativity, Faith*

Introduction

In Episode 07 of "New Habit = New Result," host Muhammad Sidik engages in a riveting conversation with Kurniawan Arif Maspul, a seasoned professional with a diverse background spanning education, entrepreneurship, and academia. Through introspection, Kurniawan shares profound insights into the pivotal role of habits in navigating the complexities of the global corporate landscape, particularly within the coffee industry.

Kurniawan reflects on his journey, emphasizing the importance of perpetual growth and goal-oriented thinking. He highlights key milestones, from educational endeavors in Indonesia to entrepreneurial ventures in the UAE and Saudi Arabia, all while pursuing advanced academic qualifications. Delving into his habits, Kurniawan discusses disciplined approaches to cognition and the ritualistic consumption of coffee as a cognitive enhancer. He underscores the synergy between spiritual grounding and resilience in overcoming challenges.

Kurniawan elucidates his method for habit formation, advocating for process-driven frameworks and integrating positive behaviors into daily routines. He shares aspirations for cultivating new habits in business and academia, emphasizing patience and perseverance. Offering pragmatic advice, Kurniawan emphasizes the importance of mental well-being, dietary consciousness, and physical vitality in fostering sustainable habits. He champions a proactive ethos of problem-solving and resilience. In a poignant message, Kurniawan encourages listeners to harness creativity and pursue greatness while anchoring themselves in spirituality and faith.

Method

The method employed for conducting the podcast session involved several steps to ensure a smooth and engaging experience for both the host and the guest. Firstly, the host scheduled the session and invited Kurniawan Arif Maspul to participate via Zoom. Prior to the session, the host prepared a list of questions covering various topics, including Kurniawan's background, career journey, habits, and tips for success. During the session, the host facilitated the conversation, posing questions and encouraging Kurniawan to share his insights and experiences. The discussion was recorded in real-time using Zoom recording feature to preserve the content for future reference. Following the session, the recording was edited, if necessary, to enhance clarity and remove any technical glitches. Finally, the edited recording was uploaded to Spotify to make it accessible to a wider audience.

Q&A Discussion

Episode 07: Building Excellent Habits with *Mas* Kurniawan Arif Maspul

"Hello Distco Friends! Welcome to 'New Habit = New Result'. I'm your host Muhammad Sidik, a coach in the field of transformation, people development, and organizational development. This episode is very special because we will have a conversation with *Mas* Kurniawan Arif Maspul, a professional who has embarked on a long and fascinating journey spanning various fields including Education, then the coffee business, and also writing books and conducting research, and now as one of the Indonesian diaspora residing and working abroad. Let's explore the great habits that have guided him through the challenges of the global corporate world, especially regarding the 'coffee' industry."

Question 1: Introduction

"Hello Mas Kurniawan! What do your friends call you? Please share a bit about yourself, your career journey, and what has led you to this point."

In my perspective, there is no endpoint in the meaning of completion. My life philosophy demands constant leadership, wherein I view processes as continuously evolving towards new goals. This perpetual cycle of setting and achieving goals has become ingrained in my ethos.

I hail from an ordinary family in Palangkaraya, devoid of any background in education or entrepreneurship. My upbringing was uneventful until I entered boarding schools in Banjar*Masin* and Madura. Here, I began to assimilate into societal norms, delving into human behavior and constantly

seeking ways to better myself. In 2006, I was awarded three scholarships to UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, Al Azhar Cairo, and Islamic University Madinah. Opting for the latter, I embarked on a journey that deepened my understanding of religion, broadened my cultural horizons through extensive travel, and nurtured a passion for exploration.

Upon my return in 2013, I assumed the role of Vice Principal at a Jakarta high school. Subsequently, I spent 3.5 years managing an educational program in Indonesia, overseeing thousands of students enrolled in tuition-free courses. My responsibilities encompassed administrative coordination, financial management, and curriculum development, facilitated through collaborative efforts with UAE-based donors. This period served as a crucible for my independent learning journey, honing my skills in management and administration.

In 2017, I transitioned to Dubai, where I ventured into entrepreneurship and embarked on a newfound passion for coffee. This marked the genesis of my exploration into the intricacies of the coffee industry, from cultivation to consumption. Over four years in the UAE, supplemented by over two additional years in Saudi Arabia, particularly in Buraydah, I dedicated myself to advancing both the professional and academic aspects of the coffee trade. Concurrently, I pursued my academic interests, completing three MBA degrees, a Master of Arts, and a Master of Education. Currently, I am pursuing a Master of Public Health at UOS (transferred to LJMU) and a Master of Islamic Banking and Finance in Malaysia.

Question 2: Daily Life and Achievements

"Currently, with your busy schedule in the coffee business, how do you maintain a balance between work and personal life?"

Balancing an eight-hour workday alongside personal pursuits is undoubtedly challenging. Constantly pondering about future aspirations, I find myself contemplating the pathways to achieve them during moments of respite or idle periods. However, achieving this equilibrium proves elusive as my ambitions are vast, yet hindered by contractual obligations that limit my ability to delve deeper into personal goals, such as pursuing a Ph.D. at a prestigious university in Indonesia or Malaysia.

Nevertheless, in the realm of coffee business, I persist in my role as an active participant within an organization that values continuous learning and identifies opportunities amidst challenges. Recognizing problems as avenues for success, I transform them into unique case studies, offering innovative solutions. This, I believe, is where balance lies - in perpetual learning and the pursuit of excellence, with every day dedicated to growth and development.

Question 3: Mas Kurniawan's Habits

"Are there any specific habits that you believe strengthen you in facing global work challenges?"

Discipline, in my opinion, is the primary key to fostering positive energy in confronting challenges. By instilling discipline within oneself, it ignites the spirit and sets clear goals to be achieved.

Additionally, indulging in coffee consumption serves as a trigger, as adequate caffeine intake stimulates our logical framework, enabling us to tackle whatever hurdles or obstacles we encounter.

Moreover, prayer plays a crucial role, as our strength ultimately comes from a higher power. As I firmly believe, God desires goodness for all individuals. Therefore, by making God the center of our goals, we open ourselves to various creative ideas and inspirations.

Question 4: Building Habits Process

"How do you develop these habits, Mas Kurniawan? Does it involve a specific process or perhaps inspiration from your experiences?"

I always believe in the process, considering it as a positive trigger in seeking solutions within our cognitive realm. For me, I never contemplate lingering at the finish line because 'finish' implies completion, and completion signifies stagnation or even death. What I mean here is not merely existing but truly living. Hence, the constant demand in my mind is as long as I am alive, I am obligated to think, and from that thinking, my positive behavior emerges, directing towards goodness. From there, various theories arise on how to accomplish tasks by constructing a positive framework within our cognitive and behavioral pyramid of thinking.

This process begins as soon as I wake up and during my morning routine. I am so accustomed to contemplating what I will do each day while showering that it naturally unfolds the tasks I will undertake. The pathway organically forms, leaving only the practical implementation to follow. Additionally, during idle moments, whenever my thoughts wander, I always invoke, "O Allah, facilitate my affairs!" That's about it.

Question 5: Desire for New Habits

"Everyone has felt the desire to change certain habits. How about you, Mas Kurniawan? Have you ever felt the need to change a habit?"

Currently, I haven't felt the need to change any habits, but there's one habit I dislike, which is eating out excessively, as it's not sustainable. This habit developed during my time in Dubai, where seeking culinary satisfaction became more of a lifestyle. On the other hand, regarding new habits, I aspire to manage my own business, particularly in the coffee value chain, and pursue my doctoral studies. However, for now, I'm continuing my studies online, so patience is key as I strive to develop academically until I can complete the two degrees I've yet to finish. Another desire is to become more active in note-taking, as my bad habit is relying on memory instead of jotting down tasks or activities I've completed. This, admittedly, is one of my shortcomings.

Question 6: Factors for Successfully Changing Habits

"For our friends at Distco who may also want to change their habits, in your opinion, Mas Kurniawan, what are the key factors for success they should consider?"

The crucial factors for success lie in mental well-being, starting with dietary habits. I'm not referring solely to physical health but also how food shapes our thinking patterns and personalities. Besides adhering to halal principles, it's important to avoid foods that hinder sustained activity. For instance, anything high in sugar should be replaced with natural sweetness from fruits and vegetables. Alongside nutrition, maintaining a rhythm of physical activity is essential. Incorporating activities like walking or cardio exercises can optimize blood circulation, making it easier for us to think clearly. Ultimately, the goal is to turn these cognitive activities into positive habits. By adopting a mindset of problem-solving and embracing challenges, we can cultivate a habit of proactive thinking through logical frameworks.

Question 7: Tips and Messages for Distco Friends

"Lastly, Mas Kurniawan, do you have any messages or tips you'd like to share with our audience? Perhaps something to inspire them in pursuing positive change?"

"Be creative and achieve greatness" is always my advice to those around me. Life is short; we might not live to see tomorrow, who knows. Therefore, leave behind a positive legacy in your community or society. There are many ways to do this, such as starting a podcast, writing, and more. Maximize your activities by recording them so that others can benefit from them. And if you believe you've crafted a grand plan for life, don't forget about God, as He is the one who gives meaning to our lives for our families and society.

Figure 1, Q&A through Zoom platform

Closing

"Dear Distco Friends, that concludes our inspiring interview with Kurniawan, an inspirational figure as an Indonesian diaspora. Thank you, Kurniawan, for your time and valuable insights. To our Distco listeners, don't miss the next episode of 'New Habit = New Result' only on Distco, Discover through Coaching. Until then, farewell and here's to creating new habits for better results!"